

AEROELASTIC OPTIMUM DESIGN OF COMPOSITE ROTOR BLADE WITH RETURNING WAKE EFFECT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, an optimum design of the helicopter rotor blade made of graphite/epoxy composite material is attempted.

The rotor blade is modeled as a laminated plate and ply angles are design variables. Four vibration modes are assumed through the combination of two spanwise mode shapes and two chordwise mode shapes which results in the first and the second bending modes and the first and the second torsion modes of the plate.

The significant difference from the previous work is the application of unsteady aerodynamics with returning wake effect which is not necessary in the fixed wing problem.

The flutter angular velocities as the starting point of the aeroelastic instability are computed by using the solution technique similar to V-g method. A ply angle at the maximum flutter angular velocity is chosen as an optimum design.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the high specific stiffness and strength of the advanced composite materials, research works for their uses have been tremendous and applications to aircraft structures of the materials are also getting popular. Specially, active use of the directionality of the advanced composites enables us to tailor the dynamic frequencies of aircraft wings and helicopter rotor blades. As results, the aircraft structures become aeroelastically stable with excellent aerodynamic maneuverability and less weight. Application of these research results to the composite hingeless rotor system of the Sikorsky UTTAS helicopter reduced parts count by 25 percent, weight by 30 percent and manufacturing costs by 20 percent. The reduced parts counts and weight mean less cost for maintenance and operation through the life time of the helicopters.^{1,2} In rotary wing aeroelasticity,³⁻⁸ two dimensional quasi-steady or unsteady incompressible aerodynamics were generally used.

In this study, idealizing a rotary wing by symmetrically laminated plate, the natural frequencies and the flutter speeds for various ply angle are calculated. A Rayleigh-Ritz formulation is used by assuming four vibration modes involving two bending modes(1B,2B) and two torsion modes(1T,2T). An unsteady, incompressible two dimensional aerodynamic theory using Lowey's function with returning shed wake is utilized, and the computed flutter speeds are compared with those using Theodorsen's. High nonlinearities of the resulting equations are solved by adopting V-g method and manipulating the relationship between rotating rotor speed and reduced frequency.

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Lateral deflection for two bending modes(1B,2B) and two torsion modes(1T,2T) is assumed by

$$w = \sum_{i=1}^4 \gamma_i(x,y) q_i(t) \quad (1)$$

The assumed mode shapes can be written as products $\gamma_i(x,y) = \phi_i(x)\psi_i(y)$, given by^{9,10}

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1(x) &= \cosh(\epsilon_i x/l) - \cos(\epsilon_i x/l) - \eta_i [\sinh(\epsilon_i x/l) - \sin(\epsilon_i x/l)] & i=1,2 \\ \phi_3(x) &= \sin(\pi x/2l), & \phi_4(x) = \sin(3\pi x/2l) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\psi_1(y) = \psi_2(y) = 1, \quad \psi_3(y) = \psi_4(y) = y/c$$

$$\epsilon_1 = 1.87510407, \quad \epsilon_2 = 4.69409113, \quad \eta_1 = 0.73409551, \quad \eta_2 = 1.01846732$$

The bending strain energy for a symmetrically laminated plate is ¹¹

$$U_b = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \int_{-b}^b [D_{11}(w_{,xx})^2 + 2D_{12}w_{,xx}w_{,yy} + D_{22}(w_{,xx})^2 + 4D_{16}w_{,xx}w_{,xy} + 4D_{26}w_{,xx}w_{,xy} + 4D_{66}(w_{,xy})^2] dx dy \quad (3)$$

where D_{ij} denotes flexural modulus for an n-ply laminate defined as ¹²

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \quad (4)$$

The potential energy of in-plane forces is ¹³

$$U_p = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \int_{-b}^b [N_x(w_{,x})^2 + N_y(w_{,y})^2 + 2N_{xy}w_{,x}w_{,y}] dy dx \quad (5)$$

where N_x, N_y, N_{xy} are approximated by ^{14,15}

$$N_x = \int_X^{r_0+l} m \Omega^2 X dX, \quad N_y = \int_Y^{b \cos \theta} m \Omega^2 Y dY, \quad N_{xy} = 0 \quad (6)$$

So the total potential energy U is the summation of U_b and U_p , given by

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \int_0^l \int_{-b}^b [D_{11} \gamma_{i,xx} \gamma_{j,xx} + D_{12} (\gamma_{i,xx} \gamma_{j,yy} + \gamma_{i,yy} \gamma_{j,xx}) + D_{22} \gamma_{i,xx} \gamma_{j,yy} + 2D_{16} (\gamma_{i,xx} \gamma_{j,xy} + \gamma_{i,xy} \gamma_{j,xx}) + 2D_{26} (\gamma_{i,yy} \gamma_{j,xy} + \gamma_{i,xy} \gamma_{j,yy}) + 4D_{66} \gamma_{i,xy} \gamma_{j,xy}] + \frac{1}{2} m \Omega^2 \{ (r_0+l)^2 - (r_0+x)^2 \} \gamma_{i,x} \gamma_{j,x} + (b^2 - y^2) \cos^2 \theta \gamma_{i,y} \gamma_{j,y}] dy dx q_i q_j \quad (7)$$

Neglecting the term which gives rise to Coriolis effect, the kinetic energy of the rotary wing can be written as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \int_{-b}^b m [\sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \gamma_i \dot{q}_i \dot{q}_j + \Omega^2 \{ (r_0+x)^2 + y^2 \cos^2 \theta - 2y \cos \theta \sin \theta \sum_{i=1}^4 \gamma_i q_i + \sin^2 \theta \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \gamma_i \gamma_j q_i q_j]] dy dx \quad (8)$$

The external virtual work of the aerodynamic forces can be expressed as

$$\delta W = \sum_{i=1}^4 \int_0^l \int_{-b}^b \Delta p(x,y) \gamma_i(x,y) dy dx \delta q_i = \sum_{i=1}^4 Q_i \delta q_i \quad (9)$$

From this relation, the generalized forces can be found.

$$Q_i = \int_0^l L \phi_i dx \quad \text{for } i=1,2 \quad Q_i = 1/c \int_0^l M \phi_i dx \quad \text{for } i=3,4 \quad (10)$$

The equation of motion can be obtained by Lagrange's equation.

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{f} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{A} are mass, stiffness and aerodynamic matrices, respectively, and \mathbf{f} is centrifugal force vector. And stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} can be separated into \mathbf{K}^n without Ω and \mathbf{K}^Ω with Ω .

AERODYNAMIC ANALYSIS

A rotor in hovering trails a tip vortex which is blown axially downward so that it would form a contracting helix as shown in Fig.2. If the inflow over the rotor disc, u , is assumed to be constant, then the fluid that comes off the trailing edge of the blade makes a helical surface. Fig.2 illustrates two cases which are high inflow(Fig.2a) and low inflow(Fig.2b). In this study, the case of low inflow is considered. In order to simplify the problems, the followings will be assumed.

A. The surfaces of the wake spiral below the blade are modeled by series of planar, two dimensional vortex sheets with vertical separation \bar{h} that extend from infinity upstream to down stream.

B. All the wake vortex sheets are parallel to the free stream velocity.

The lift deficiency function by above assumptions is

$$C'(k, p, \bar{h}) = \frac{H_1^{(2)}(k) + 2J_1(k)W}{H_1^{(2)}(k) + iH_0^{(2)}(k) + 2[J_1(k) + iJ_0(k)]W} \quad (12)$$

where W is the term having the effect of returning shed wake, and Lowey's function C' becomes Theodorsen function C when W is zero.¹⁶

If the elastic axis is equal to the geometric center, lift L and moment M for the rotary wing with harmonic motion ($q_i = q_i^0 + \bar{q}_i e^{i\omega t}$) becomes^{9,17}

$$L = \pi \rho b^2 \omega^2 e^{i\omega t} [L_h(\phi_1 \bar{q}_1 + \phi_2 \bar{q}_2) + L_\alpha(\phi_3 \bar{q}_3 + \phi_4 \bar{q}_4)] + L_s \quad (13)$$

$$M = \pi \rho b^3 \omega^2 e^{i\omega t} [M_h(\phi_1 \bar{q}_1 + \phi_2 \bar{q}_2) + M_\alpha(\phi_3 \bar{q}_3 + \phi_4 \bar{q}_4)] + M_s \quad (14)$$

where $L_h, L_\alpha, L_s, M_h, M_\alpha, M_s$ are given as

$$\begin{aligned} L_h &= \cos\theta + \theta \sin\theta - i/2k [C'(\cos\theta + \theta \sin\theta) + \theta \sin\theta], \quad L_\alpha = i/2k + iC'/2k + C'/k^2 \\ L_s &= 2\pi \rho b (r_0 + x)^2 \Omega^2 [\theta(1+C') + C'(\phi_3 q_3 + \phi_4 q_4)/c], \quad M_h = -i/k [C' \cos\theta + (1+C')\theta \sin\theta] \\ M_\alpha &= 1/16 - i/4k + iC'/4k + C'/2k^2, \quad M_s = \pi \rho b^2 (r_0 + x)^2 \Omega^2 [\theta(1+C') + C'(\phi_3 q_3 + \phi_4 q_4)] \end{aligned}$$

Substituting L and M into Eq.(10), the matrix form of the generalized forces is

$$\mathbf{Q} = \pi \rho b^2 \omega^2 e^{i\omega t} \mathbf{A} \bar{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{q}^0 + \mathbf{a} \quad (15)$$

METHOD OF SOLUTION

As results, the final dynamic equation of motion is

$$[\mathbf{K} - \omega^2(\mathbf{M} + \pi \rho b^2 \mathbf{A})] \bar{\mathbf{q}} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Free vibration analysis can be performed by neglecting the aerodynamic term \mathbf{A} in Eq.(16).

$$[(\mathbf{K}^n + \mathbf{K}^\Omega) - \omega^2 \mathbf{M}] \bar{\mathbf{q}} = 0 \quad (17)$$

This standard real eigenvalue problem is solved for eigenvalue ω_i^2 and associated q_i when \mathbf{K}^Ω is zero or nonzero. And ω_i for rotating blade are calculated by increasing the angular speed of rotor Ω .

Rewriting \mathbf{K} in terms of \mathbf{K}^n and \mathbf{K}^Ω , Eq.(16) becomes

$$[(\mathbf{K}^n + \mathbf{K}^\Omega) - \omega^2(\mathbf{M} + \pi \rho b^2 \mathbf{A})] \bar{\mathbf{q}} = 0 \quad (18)$$

Since Ω and ω are unknowns, Eq.(18) is nonlinear and it is impossible to use directly V-g method. Therefore using the relation $k = \omega b / \Omega r$, \mathbf{K}^k the function of k is defined as $\omega^2 \mathbf{K}^k = \mathbf{K}^\Omega$. Structural damping is introduced by multiplying \mathbf{K}^n by $1 + ig$ where g is the damping needed for stabilizing rotor blade. Flutter is occurred when g becomes positive value. A complex eigenvalue defined as $Z = (1 + ig) / (\omega^2)$ allows the equation of motion to be written as a standard complex eigenvalue problem,

$$[(\mathbf{M} + \pi \rho b^2 \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{K}^k) - Z \mathbf{K}] \bar{\mathbf{q}} = 0 \quad (19)$$

For each Z_i , the frequency ω , the structural damping g , and rotational flutter speed are found through the relations

$$\omega = 1/\sqrt{\text{Re}(Z)}, \quad g = \text{Im}(Z)/\text{Re}(Z), \quad \Omega = b\omega/k(r_0 + x_{10}) \quad (20)$$

Because the rotating speed of rotor blade changes through the span, the reduced frequency doesn't have constant value. Therefore the evaluation of aerodynamic matrix \mathbf{A} is performed by using 10 point Gauss integration and the reference value of k is selected as that of integraton point x_0 nearest at blade tip. The reference frequencies k_i at each integration point are calculated from the the relations

$$k = \omega b / \Omega (r_0 + x_{10}), \quad k_i = k (r_0 + x_{10}) / (r_0 + x_i) \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 10 \quad (21)$$

The above procedure is repeated by decreasing k values until g has zero value. When the g value zero, ω and Ω are the flutter frequency and the angular flutter speed respectively. Computer code is programmed by using EIGZC of IMSL which extracts complex eigenvalues.¹⁸

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The properties of used graphite/epoxy prepreg and dimensions of rotary wing are as follows.

$$E_1 = 117.83 \text{ Gpa}, \quad E_2 = 7.63 \text{ Gpa}, \quad G_{12} = 4.68 \text{ Gpa}, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.27, \quad t = 0.175 \text{ mm}, \\ m = 1520 \text{ kg/m}^3, \quad l = 64 \text{ cm}, \quad c = 8 \text{ cm}, \quad r_0 = 0 \text{ cm}, \quad \theta = 5^\circ, \quad \rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

The composite laminated plates have the stacking sequence such as $[\theta_p]_{10T}$ and calculation was performed by varying θ_p as $0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ, 90^\circ$. The variation of natural frequency was obtained for the angular speeds of rotor from 0 to 1000 rpm. Fig.3 and Fig.4 show natural frequencies vs. fiber sweep angles of 1B and 1T, respectively. From these, it is clear that the natural frequency of the bending mode is large at the ply angle 0° and that of the torsion mode is maximum at the ply angle 45° . Note that the case of $\theta_p = 90^\circ$ has the undesirable vibration behavior for both bending and torsion. The result suggests that the appropriate manipulation of ply angles give the good characteristics of vibration for both bending and torsion.

As the angular speed of rotor increases, natural frequencies of the first bending do rapidly and converge to a constant value as shown in Fig.5 because rotational effect is great. On the other hand, Fig.6 shows natural frequencies of the second torsion as rotating, and the rotational effect is relatively small for bending. Fig.7 shows natural frequencies of 1T and 2B for $\theta_p = 90^\circ$ as rotating. This result indicates that the reinforcement of torsional stiffness is necessary for a rotating blade.

Fig.8 shows $\Omega-g$ diagram of $[0^\circ]_{10T}$ similar to $V-g$ diagram for the fixed wing. $\Omega-g$ diagram of the other ply angle is similar to that in Fig.8. The flutter of bending mode was not occurred for all ply angles and this result is due to the stiffening effect by rotating. The flutter speed is large near $\theta_p = 45^\circ$.

The typical $\Omega-g$ and $\Omega-\omega_f$ diagrams of $[0^\circ]_{10T}$ plate for 2T mode are shown in Fig.9 where the results of the different functions i.e. Theodorsen's and Lowey's are compared. From these figures, it is seen that the flutter speed is smaller in the case using Lowey's function than the case doing Theodorsen's. Therefore it is necessary to take account into the effect of the returnig shed wake for the flutter analysis of rotary wings.

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Fig.1 Rotating Cantilevered Blade System

Fig.2 Schematic Representation of Unsteady Rotor Flow Field

Fig.3 Natural Frequency vs. Ply Angle for 1B Mode

Fig.4 Natural Frequency vs. Ply Angle for 1T Mode

Fig.5 Natural Frequency vs. Rotational Speed for 1B Mode

Fig.6 Natural Frequency vs. Rotational Speed for 2T Mode

Fig.7 Natural Frequency vs. Rotational Speed for 1T and 2B of $[90^0]_{10R}$

Fig.8 Ω -g Diagram for $[0^0]_{10R}$ Plate

$\Omega - g$ Diagram for 2T Mode
of $[0^6]_{10r}$ Plate

$\Omega - \omega_y$ Diagram for 2T Mode
of $[0^6]_{10r}$ Plate

Fig.9